

EU Cross-border Cooperation in Eastern Europe

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Abstract. *The paper presents research results of the EU's cross-border cooperation initiatives in the Eastern Europe, especially in the countries of Eastern Partnership. Considering the implementation history of cross-border cooperation projects, the European Union initiated, developed and follows up the policy of dialogue with its Eastern European neighbours in a short and long run. The focus strives at presenting the framework of cross-border cooperation of the European Union in the Eastern Europe, especially with the Eastern Partnership countries; the initiatives and good practices in the field. The results of EU cross-border cooperation in the Eastern Europe display differentiation of collaboration and development in peculiar aspects of common interest for participating countries.*

Keywords: *European Union, cross-border cooperation, Eastern Europe, Eastern Partnership, dialogue, development*

Introduction

Cross-border cooperation initiatives have a distinct place in the European integration process. The policy of cross-border cooperation has affected both the Member States and the neighbours of the European Union. These target countries benefited the same attention from the European Union's cooperation instruments of various types.

Cross-border cooperation refers to relations between the Member States and the non-Member States; transnational cooperation refers to relations with outside EU countries that have borders with the European Union. Cross-border cooperation in Eastern Europe was and still is of great importance both for the European Union and its neighbours. The Eastern Partnership countries have participated in different EU cross-border initiatives. As a result many of them are members in various Euroregions, having access to European tools of development.

The Eastern Partnership countries present a special interest in cross-border cooperation both for the European Union and the six countries of the partnership. Neighbours of the neighbours are also very interested in this cooperation as well, but from another perspective. Cross-border cooperation in the Eastern Partnership varies from region to region taking into consideration manifested interests and local peculiarities. The European Union has started with general and common provisions by diversifying the collaboration instruments to differentiation and specialization. In doing such introspection it is fair to begin with a division of Europe to see exactly the place and role of the Eastern Partnership countries.

Eastern Europe: Division. The United Nations Statistics Division includes ten states, belonging to Eastern Europe: Belarus, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia and Ukraine. The grouping serves for statistical convenience without focusing on affiliation basis. However, a clear distinction makes them to former Warsaw Pact.

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Figure 1. Eastern Europe

Source: “Map of Europe with Countries,” accessed March 18, 2016, <http://www.worldatlasbook.com/images/maps/europe-map-countries.jpg>.

Figure 2. Eastern Europe

Source: “Europe Subregion Map World Factbook.svg,” accessed March 18, 2016, https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Europe_subregion_map_world_factbook.svg.

Another division for Eastern Europe is available in The World Factbook. This source includes such countries in the Eastern Europe: Belarus, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia (transcontinental), Turkey (transcontinental) and Ukraine.

Irrespective of the principles of grouping, the Eastern Partnership countries are present in both divisions, which constitute an interested area of cross-border cooperation. The Eastern Partnership countries are situated in the Eastern Europe, which are in immediate position to the Eastern Borders of the European Union. As the European Union has constantly promoted cross-border cooperation programmes, all Eastern Europe's countries and Eastern Partnership countries have been eligible for and became partners in running cooperation projects.

European Territorial Cooperation (ETC)

The European territorial cooperation is a result of melting borders. Joachim Beck's assertion is programmatic in this sense as he said that "a bird flying over the Upper Rhine sees no borders. The challenge is how to make this happen on the ground"¹.

In fact, the European territorial cooperation was formalized recently as a policy of the European Union. The European territorial cooperation "describes partnerships established between the regional or local authorities of one European state on the one hand and the equivalent authorities in one or more other European states on the other hand with a view to developing joint initiatives or addressing problems they regard as comparable"². The European territorial cooperation inside and outside the European Union is a tool that answers to social needs, makes people's lives easier and better, and solve problems people and states face in their development.

The European territorial cooperation, known as Interreg, is one of the two goals of cohesion policy and provides a framework for the implementation of joint actions and policy exchanges between national, regional and local actors from different Member States. The overarching objective of European territorial cooperation is to promote a harmonious economic, social and territorial development of the Union as a whole³. The European territorial cooperation falls under three strands of cooperation: cross-border (Interreg A) for areas separated by an EU border, as well as for those bordering (potential) candidate countries; transnational (Interreg B) for a specific larger area like the Alpine Space; and interregional (Interreg C) for all EU regions. Five programming periods of Interreg have succeeded each other: Interreg I (1990–1993); Interreg II (1994–1999); Interreg III (2000–2006); Interreg IV (2007–2013); and Interreg V (2014–2020).

As regards Interreg 2014–2020, the key elements are concentration, simplification and results orientation. Interreg 2014–2020 regulation presents eleven priorities: strengthening research, technological development and innovation; enhancing access to and use and quality of ICT; enhancing the competitiveness of SMEs; supporting the shift towards a low-carbon economy in all sectors; promoting climate change adaptation, risk prevention and management; protecting the environment and promoting resource efficiency; promoting sustainable transport and removing bottlenecks in key network infrastructures; promoting employment and supporting labour mobility; promoting social

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Regional Policy, *European Territorial Cooperation: Building Bridges between People* (Brussels: European Commission, 2011), 6.

² Birte Wassenberg, Bernard Reitel, and Jean Peyrony Rubio, eds, *Territorial Cooperation in Europe: A Historical Perspective* (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2015), 6.

³ Cf. European Commission, "Interreg: European Territorial Co-operation," accessed January 10, 2016, http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/cooperation/european-territorial/.

inclusion and combating poverty; investing in education, skills and lifelong learning by developing education and training infrastructure; enhancing institutional capacity and an efficient public administration.

Interreg 2014–2020 has a budget of EUR 10.1 billion invested in over 100 cooperation programmes between regions and territorial, social and economic partners. This budget also includes the ERDF allocation for Member States to participate in EU external border cooperation programmes supported by other instruments (Instrument for Pre-Accession and European Neighbourhood Instrument). The total budget of Interreg 2014–2020 provides a platform for making an exchange of experiences and good practices that fall under cross-border, transnational and interregional cooperation in Europe. Each strand has its own financial instruments, which are specific for various areas of cooperation. Synoptically the table comprises the overall budget.

Table 1. *Interreg 2014–2020 Budget*

Source: European Commission, “Interreg: European Territorial Cooperation,” accessed January 10, 2016, http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/cooperation/european-territorial/.

The allocated funds for the European territorial cooperation are very substantial and answer respectively to programming ambitions to increase the quality of life and to deal with a proper cohesion policy.

Cross-border cooperation

The provisions on cross-border cooperation were generated by the realities on borderlands and of borderlanders. Before European integration process, the borders played the role of barriers – legal, administrative, economic, physical. During the integration process, the borderlands and the borderlanders became inlands and inlanders. Before, the borderlands were often peripheral, undeveloped and marginalised. After, becoming inlands, these areas faced common problems to be solved, irrespective from the side. A

working tool for developing cross-border cooperation – both of the Member States and of candidate or potential candidate countries – resides in implementing programmes for such a purpose. Usually, the programme refers to: repairing and (re)building roads, paths or bridges; investing in waste systems, medical equipment, anti-flood measures, and so on; managing natural or tourism sites; developing common services for the local population; advising on employment issues; and creating thematic networks and clusters for innovation⁴.

Figure 3. Border Cooperation in Europe

Source: “Le regioni d’Europa, classificate per tipo” [The regions of Europe classified by type], accessed February 28, 2016, http://emiliodalessio.blogspot.md/2016_01_01_archive.html.

Transnational Cooperation

This type of cooperation implies national, regional and local authorities across the European Union to promote better integration. Usually the programme refers to such challenges that could be faced only by a collective action on a transnational level. It includes: water management, risk prevention, energy efficiency and environmental protection activities; technology transfers; developing common services for the local

⁴ European Commission, Directorate-General for Regional Policy, *European Territorial Cooperation*, 12.

population; developing joint financial engineering instruments to support research and development in SMEs; activities to improve access to and the quality of transport and telecoms services; and fostering sustainable urban development⁵.

Figure 4. *Transnational Cooperation 2007–2013*

Source: European Commission, “Interreg: European Territorial Cooperation.”

The current Interreg B covers fifteen cooperation programmes for transnational cooperation.

⁵ Ibid., 14.

Figure 5. *Transnational Cooperation 2014–2020*

Source: European Commission, “Interreg: European Territorial Cooperation.”

These platforms promote meaningful work between regions from several EU Member States on matters such as communication corridors, flood management, international business and research linkages, and the development of more viable and sustainable markets. Themes comprise: innovation, especially networks of universities, research institutions, SMEs; environment, especially water resources, rivers, lakes, sea; accessibility, including telecommunications, and in particular the completion of networks; sustainable urban development, especially polycentric development⁶.

Interregional Cooperation

Interregional cooperation is a key programme of working together between regions all over Europe. Interregional cooperation links regions and cities in Europe to work on issues of common interest, share good ideas and existing answers to problems, and develop new solutions. Regional and local actors, including those from Norway and Switzerland, participate in networks, for example, to make our cities greener, improve energy efficiency of buildings or enhance innovation in SMEs⁷. Cooperation and cohesion is realized through such instruments as INTERACT and ESPON.

⁶ European Commission, “Interreg B – Transnational Cooperation,” accessed January 12, 2016, http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/cooperation/european-territorial/trans-national/.

⁷ European Commission, Directorate-General for Regional Policy, *European Territorial Cooperation*, 16.

Figure 6. *Interregional Cooperation*

Source: “Interregional Cooperation Programme Interreg Europe,” accessed February 12, 2016, http://www.strukturalni-fondy.cz/getmedia/7ded87c9-926f-4723-b012-975562797d35/INTERREG_4_20_201406.jpg.

Euroregions: Eastern Europe

The concept of Euroregions is viable in a united Europe and represents the effect of European integration. The Euroregions are associative and networking structures, which bring together regions in order to achieve a sustainable management of their territories according to the specific needs.

The Euroregions have supported cross-border cooperation in the European Union, between the Member States and their non-EU neighbours. The Euroregions have contributed to redraw a new political map of Europe, by reducing the barrier effect and reinforcing common development strategies for better life and social security.

Surprisingly, the European Union has promoted many associative and networking structures at its Eastern borders from North to South. Some of these Euroregions are very active players in the Eastern Europe, while others consolidate their capacities in the field of cross-border cooperation.

The synopsis comprises Neman Euroregion, Ozerny Krai Euroregion, Białowieża Forest Euroregion, Bug Euroregion, Dnepr Euroregion, Carpathian Euroregion, Upper Prut Euroregion, Siret-Prut-Nistru Euroregion, Lower Danube Euroregion, and Dniester Euroregion. Moreover, the European Union’s strategy is presented on the Baltic Sea Region and the Danube Region.

Neman Euroregion

The Agreement on creation of Neman Euroregion was signed on June 6, 1997. Neman Euroregion unites Grodno region (Belarus), Podlaska voivodship (Poland), Mariampol, Alytus and Vilnius regions (Lithuania), Cherniakhov, Krasnoznamensk, Ozersk, Gusev and Nesterov districts of Kaliningrad region (Russia).

Main water way of the Euroregion is river Neman, which is the third largest river in Belarus. Its length is 937 km. As far as Euroregion covers a territory in four countries it

is of great importance for the region to develop transport and communication systems together with tourism infrastructure, roadside service.

Figure 7. *Neman Euroregion*

Source: “Koordinazioni biuro Evroregiona Neman” [Coordination Bureau of Euroregion Neman], accessed March 16, 2016, <http://neman.grsu.by/ru/>.

Ozerny Krai Euroregion

Ozerny Krai Euroregion includes Braslav district, Verkhnedvinsk district, Miorsk district, Postavy district and Gluboks district (Belarus); Duagavpils district, Kraslava district, Preili district, Rezekne district (Latvia); Zarasai district, Ignalina district, Utena district and Svencionys district, including Visaginas city (Lithuania).

The area of the Euroregion is a model for landscapes of Baltic Lakeland. Distinctive features of the Euroregion are favorable natural-climatic conditions, attractive landscapes and presence of natural-recreation resources providing leisure time.

The Euroregion has considerable cultural-historic resources, represented by monumental objects of historical-cultural heritage, handicrafts, museums, expositions and regular events (festivals, fairs, competitions, etc.).

Different companies on the territory of the Euroregion represent mainly food industry, processing and light industry.

The development of rural tourism in the Euroregion facilitates sustainable demand to local goods, which can become a kind of support to local agricultural production and service sphere.

Figure 8. Ozerny Krai Euroregion

Source: "Euroregion 'Ozerny krai'," accessed March 11, 2016, http://beleuroregion.by/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=63&Itemid=96&lang=en.

Figure 9. Białowieża Forest Euroregion

BELOVEZHSKAYA PUSHCHA / BIALOWIEZA FOREST
Belarus / Poland

Source: "Map of Białowieża Forest Euroregion," accessed March 11, 2016, <http://www.euroregion-pb.pl/wordpress/czlonkowie-euroregionu/>.

Białowieża Forest Euroregion

The Euroregion unites Kamyanyets, Pruzhany, Svislac districts (Belarus) and Hajnowka county (Poland). The Euroregion shows its willingness to mutually beneficial cross-border cooperation on the territory of Belarus and Poland, where a unique complex of relict woods of Białowieża Forest is located.

The name of the Euroregion, on its own, tells that the main natural attraction of the Euroregion is unique, the biggest wood of Europe. The average age of trees in Białowieża Forest is more than 100 years; other parts of the wood have an average age of 250–350 years. There are more than a thousand giant trees registered in Białowieża Forest. Białowieża Forest has the largest number of various species of animals and plants in the whole Europe.

Białowieża Forest has a well-developed touristic infrastructure: numerous places for rest, ethnographic museum-reserve of forest road, observation platform, observation tower, bridges and educational tables.

Bug Euroregion

The cross-border union Bug Euroregion includes the following members: Brest region (Belarus), Lublin province (Poland), and Volyn region (Ukraine).

Figure 10. *Bug Euroregion*

Source: “Map of Bug Euroregion,” accessed February 20, 2016, http://beleuroregion.by/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=60&lang=en.

On the territory of the Euroregion there are several national parks:

- Białowieża (in Belarus and Poland) on a territory of 87,6 thousand hectares, it comprises the only primeval wood in Europe, which has more than several thousand species of mostly unique animals and plants;

- Polesie (in Poland);
- Rostocze (in Poland), with rare landscapes, combining flat peaks, abrupt slopes and deep cut valleys;
- Shatsky (in Ukraine), it includes 22 lakes of karstic and post-karstic origin.

The main advantage of the Euroregion is its geographical position. Main communications go through its territory connecting countries of Eastern Europe: Russia, Ukraine, Belarus and the Baltic countries – Lithuania, Latvia and Estonia.

Developed telecommunications network, network of highways and also water way Zapadnyj Bug are common to the region.

Dnepr Euroregion

The Euroregion unites Gomel region (Belarus), Chernigov region (Ukraine) and Briansk region (Russia).

The Euroregion has many lakes and rivers. The largest navigable rivers are Dnepr, Sozh, Pripyat. The Euroregion has enough favorable natural conditions for development of all spheres of human life.

Plain shape of the territory favours the development of settlements and cities, agricultural use of land, development of industrial enterprises.

Important transport ways go through the territory of the Euroregion: railways, highways, international oil pipe-line “Friendship”, gas pipelines of state importance.

There are many architectural monuments and historical-cultural places on the territory of the Euroregion.

Figure 11. *Dnepr Euroregion*

Source: “Euroregion Dnepr,” accessed February 20, 2016,

http://beleuroregion.by/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=64&Itemid=97&lang=en.

Carpathian Euroregion

The Euroregion includes 19 administrative units of five countries: Województwo Podkarpackie (Poland); Prešov kraj and Košice kraj (Slovakia), Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén county, Hajdú-Bihar county, Heves county, Jász-Nagykun-Szolnok county, and Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg county (Hungary); Bihor county, Botoșani county, Harghita county, Maramureș county, Suceava county, Satu Mare county, and Sălaj county (Romania); Tsernovtsi oblast, Ivano-Frankivsk oblast, Transcarpathian oblast, and Lviv (Lemberg) oblast (Ukraine). The mission of the Euroregion was designed to bring together the people who inhabit the region of the Carpathian Mountains and to facilitate their cooperation in the fields of science, culture, education, trade, tourism and economy.

The strategy of the Euroregion comprises four directions: (1) innovative and competitive region with a high economic potential – support for entrepreneurship, intensification of SMEs and increase of the efficient use of human resources; development of the connection between R&D and business; internal strengthening of innovation; (2) region with high social and human capital – development of education and human resources; intensification of NGOs; prevention against negative demographic trends; development of culture; (3) sustainable region – development of cities; development of transport networks, energy and telecommunication; environment and natural resources; rural development and strengthening of sustainable agriculture and forestry; tourism; (4) region of strong institutional links – promotion and branding for the region of the Carpathians; networking and promoting of international cooperation; development of the internal network and facilities.

Figure 12. Carpathian Euroregion

Source: “Map of Carpathian Euroregion,” accessed March 09, 2016, <http://www.tradecarp.com/>.

Upper Prut Euroregion

The Euroregion includes the following administrative-territorial units: Botoșani county and Suceava county (Romania); Bălți municipality, Briceni district, Edineț district, Fălești district, Glodeni district, Ocnița district, Râșcani district and Sângerei district (Moldova); Chernivtsi region and Ivano-Frankivsk region (Ukraine). The activities focus on economic projects, infrastructure, environmental projects, and cultural and humanitarian activities.

Figure 13. *Upper Prut Euroregion*

Source: “Map of Upper Prut Euroregion,” accessed March 09, 2016, https://upload.wikimedia.org/wiki/commons/thumb/4/48/Harta_GPS_calibrata_Euroregiunea_Prutul_de_Sus.jpg/988px-Harta_GPS_calibrata_Euroregiunea_Prutul_de_Sus.jpg.

Siret-Prut-Nistru Euroregion

The Euroregion the administrative units of 2 countries: Romania (Iași county, Vaslui county and Prahova county) and Moldova (26 districts out of 32, in other words the majority of the country makes part of the association).

Figure 14. *Siret-Prut-Nistru Euroregion*

Source: “Euroregiunea Siret-Prut-Nistru,” accessed March, 09, 2016, <http://www.euroregiune.org/en/>.

These Euroregions were created to provide opportunities for development and solving common problems. However, these opportunities have not been used at full extent, because of political tensions and low interest to initiate common projects⁸.

Lower Danube Euroregion

The Euroregion includes the following administrative units: Galați county, Brăila county and Tulcea county (Romania); Odessa region and Reni district (Ukraine); Cahul district and Cantemir district (Moldova). The goal is to assist the sustainable development through deepening of the cooperation between partners and of mutual relations in areas of common interest.

Figure 15. *Lower Danube Euroregion*

Source: “Euroregion Lower Danube,” accessed March 09, 2016, http://www.aebr.eu/en/members/member_detail.php?region_id=113.

⁸ James W. Scott, *EU Enlargement, Region Building and Shifting Borders of Inclusion and Exclusion* (Aldershot: Ashgate, 2006), 143.

Dniester Euroregion

The Euroregion consists of **Vinnitsa region (Ukraine)** and **Ocnîța, Soroca, Florești, Șoldănești, Rezina and Dondușeni districts (Moldova)**. The activities include: organization, coordination and intensification of cooperation in economy, science, education, culture, tourism and sports; implementation of joint projects in environmental protection of Dniester river basin; development of international transport corridors and reconstruction of existing highways; implementation of regional programs (projects) for reducing unemployment among the population of border areas; cooperation in equipping crossing points of Ukrainian-Moldovan border; organization of contacts with international organizations, foundations, institutes, agencies and other organizations.

Figure 16. *Dniester Euroregion*

Source: “Map of Dniester Euroregion,” accessed March 09, 2016, http://www.aebr.eu/en/news/news_detail.php?news_id=165.

EU Strategy

Recently the European Union has developed a macroregional strategy for cross-border cooperation all over Europe. The macroregional strategy is an integrated framework endorsed by the European Council, which may be supported by the European

Structural and Investment Funds among others, to address common challenges faced by a defined geographical area relating to Member States and third countries located in the same geographical area which thereby benefit from strengthened cooperation contributing to achievement of economic, social and territorial cohesion⁹.

So far, there are four EU macro-regional strategies:

- The EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region (2009);
- The EU Strategy for the Danube Region (2010);
- The EU Strategy for the Adriatic and Ionian Region (2014);
- The EU Strategy for the Alpine Region (2015).

Considering the Eastern European reason, two regions will be presented.

Baltic Sea Region

The EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region (2009) is the first comprehensive EU strategy to target a macro-region. Eight EU Member States form the Baltic Sea Region: Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, and Sweden. The Action Plan for the Strategy reflects the common challenges, which these countries face. The EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region includes a number of policy areas actions to save the sea, connect the region and increase prosperity – each accompanied by concrete flagships as well as by clearly identified targets and indicators. The Strategy helps to mobilize all relevant EU funding and policies and coordinate the actions of the European Union, EU countries, regions, pan-Baltic organizations, financing institutions and non-governmental bodies to promote a more balanced development of the Baltic Sea Region¹⁰. The activities focus on support for new projects, including cooperation between farmers to reduce eutrophication and improved planning for transport infrastructure; greater involvement of Russian partners in areas like environmental protection, water quality and innovation; improved cooperation between regions and other partners, including the private sector¹¹.

The EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region centres on joint problem-solving in a greater cooperation basin. The European Union Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region strives at deepening cooperation between the Baltic Sea countries in order to face easily and jointly the common problems in the region. In doing it, the European Union Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region follows the following objectives and sub-objectives: save the sea – clear water in the sea, rich and healthy wildlife, clean and safe shipping; connect the region – good transport conditions, reliable energy markets, connecting people in the region, better cooperation in fighting cross-border crime; increase prosperity – implementation of Europe 2020, improved global competitiveness of the Baltic Sea Region, climate change adaptation, risk prevention and management¹².

⁹ European Commission, “Macro-Regional Strategies,” accessed February 10, 2016, http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/cooperation/macro-regional-strategies/.

¹⁰ European Commission, “EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region,” accessed February 10, 2016, http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/cooperation/macro-regional-strategies/baltic-sea/.

¹¹ Ibid.

¹² *A Beginner’s Guide to the Baltic Sea Region Strategy* (Stockholm: Swedish Agency for Economic and Regional Growth, 2014), 5.

Figure 17. Baltic Sea Region

Source: “Interreg. Baltic Sea Region,” accessed March 09, 2016, <https://www.interreg-baltic.eu/home.html>.

Danube Region

The EU Strategy for the Danube Region (2010) is the second comprehensive EU strategy to target a macro-region. The following countries make up the Danube Region: Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia (EU members); Bosnia and Herzegovina, Moldova, Montenegro, Serbia, Ukraine (non-EU members).

The EU Strategy for the Danube Region focuses on: **faster transport** by road and rail; **cleaner transport** by improving the navigability of rivers; **cheaper and more secure energy** thanks to better connections and alternative sources; a **better environment** with cleaner water, protected biodiversity, and cross-border flood prevention; a **prosperous**

region, through working together on the economy, education, social inclusion, and research and innovation; **attractive tourist and cultural destinations**, developed and marketed jointly; a **safer, well-governed region**, thanks to better cooperation and coordination of government and non-governmental organizations. There are twelve priority areas, which strive at improving: **transport** connections, **energy** connections, the **environment**, **socio-economic** development, and **security**¹³.

Figure 18. Danube Region

Source: “Danube Region,” accessed March 09, 2016,
[http://localglobal.com/?s=danube+region#iLightbox\[gallery\]/1](http://localglobal.com/?s=danube+region#iLightbox[gallery]/1).

Conclusion

Cross-border cooperation moved European integration towards two very important horizons by deepening and enlarging the cohesion policy inside and outside the European Union. Among the beneficiaries of cross-border cooperation programmes in the Eastern Europe there have been both Member States and partner countries. Cross-border cooperation programmes with the Eastern Partnership countries play a crucial role for regional development. All in all there are political, economic and social security concerns.

The European instruments of cooperation are oriented towards stability and welfare of the people living in the Eastern Europe. Eradicating the discrepancies between the regions and the partners, it answers to cohesion policy provisions, if we consider the level of deepening the policy inside the European Union and the level of enlarging / extending it outside the European Union in the Eastern Partnership countries.

Undoubtedly, certain cross-border cooperation initiatives have been very successful due to political will and support coming from central and local authorities, others have not succeeded to develop properly.

Having learned helpful lessons from the past, the new European strategy for cross-border cooperation pleads for larger areas of collaboration that means more partners share their will to face common challenges. These new regions cover more countries with more people, just to give the example of the Baltic Sea Region or the Danube Region. The Danube Region includes both Eastern Partnership countries and Balkan countries. For sure it is a positive platform of cooperation between EU and non-EU partners, and among non-

¹³ European Commission, “EU Strategy for the Danube Region,” accessed 10 February 2016,
http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/policy/cooperation/macro-regional-strategies/danube/#2.

EU partners. The Danube River, as well as the Baltic Sea, has sufficient capacities to be a pole of stability of all kinds – political, economic, social, and security ones.

Cross-border cooperation initiatives do not represent a purpose *per se*, but the essence of being and living together in order to solve common problems of the people. Cross-border cooperation has a socio-centric nature that takes care about Europe both of EU members and EU partners.

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